

THE COMPONENTS OF THE PLOT IN JACK LONDON’S “MARTIN EDEN”

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Abstract. *This article reflects on the main factors that are framed in the content of a literary work. The genres that make up the basic structures of a novel, i.e. exposition, character development, climax, resolution, conflict, idea, and setting are the focus of this article. The exposition which is the core element, presents some basic data about the characters, time, space, and incidents in a novel. The plot of Jack London's “Martin Eden” illustrates what happens in exposition - it introduces the main character, his background, and the time and space of the novel. The importance of characters in the advancement of the plot is brought to light with the protagonist being the focal point of this analysis.*

Keywords: *exposition, climax, resolution, conflict, idea, and setting.*

A literary work consists of more than just words; it is a carefully made novel shaped by key parts that join to tell a good and big story. The novel’s full makeup rests on these parts, which help the writer show themes, emotions, and deep signs: start, character growth, climax, ending, conflicts, and place. By seeing how these bits fit together, we can better understand how a writer's aim is reflected in the novel. The content of a literary work is intended to provide information and it consists of the following components:

Exposition – This is a structural part of the plot of a literary work, which is considered to be the component of the content and it helps in the formation of events, time and space, and characters in novels. The exposition provides initial information about the characters and the places they live; it provides information about the events of a novel. The exposition is placed in various orders as one of the compositional elements of a literary work. It can be presented at the beginning, at the end, or in a scattered manner throughout the work.

For instance, Jack London provides the following information about the protagonist of the novel “Martin Eden”: Martin Eden was a man who made voyages on the sea throughout his life, and it seemed as if the smell of the ocean clung to his clothes. The young man used to walk on the deck of a ship where the sea waves made him sway up and down. One day when he came to visit his friend’s house, he saw spacious rooms in it. While entering the large rooms, Martin stumbled upon the ornaments and he was frightened to knock them down which were hanging on the mantelpiece.

Martin Eden read each sentence in the book with excitement, his face flushed as burning coal; he held the book of the famous poet Swinburne for the first time in his life; the protagonist tried to think about the poet Swinburne. He was so obsessed with reading the books on the bookcase that he did not notice a girl entering the room. For the first time in his life, Martin Eden was addressed as "Mister"; on hearing "Mister Martin Eden," he was startled. The deuteragonist Ruth Morse stood in front of him; she was depicted as a gorgeous girl who had blue eyes and a delicate figure, golden hair, and grace. In this way, Jack London formed the exposition in the novel “Martin Eden.”

Character – plays an important role in the development of the plot in a novel. For instance, Martin Eden, Ruth Morse, Arthur, and Gertrude are the characters of the novel “Martin Eden”.

Climax – is a component that emphasizes the main content of the literary work and it represents the peak of the events. The climax is when Martin Iden is treated better after achieving fame in the novel “Martin Iden”.

Resolution – is a component that brings the events of the literary work to a conclusion. It seemed to Martin as if he were a useless person in the materialistic society in the novel “Martin Iden”. He no longer wishes to return to the group of people from his own class, whom he once loved. The ideal life Martin dreamed of did not bring him happiness; on the contrary, his successful life began to torture him. He embarks on a journey in a high-class cabin for the first time in his life, but his committing suicide shows the ending of the novel.

Conflict – is a clash and struggle between characters in a literary work. In Jack London's novel “Hearts of Three”, the protagonist, Francis Morgan, experiences conflict with the characters Alvares Torres and Thomas Rigan, which paves the way for the development of the plot.

Idea – is an author’s main concept expressed in the literary work. Jack London’s main concept in the novel “Martin Eden” is to describe real-life events of the society.

Setting – is a component that shows the time and place of the literary work. The events of the novel “Martin Eden” take place at the end of the 19th century and at the beginning of the 20th century, during a period when members of the middle class were gaining their high status in society.

To sum up, the novel “Martin Eden” is written with careful observation of the society and the writer intends to show social issues of real life. The start shows us the characters, places, and happenings, and sets up in the novel. Martin Eden in Jack London’s novel is the main hero in moving the plot along and the protagonist in “Martin Eden” faces his own struggles with society. The climax in the novel can be determined when the protagonist becomes popular in the world, however, he does not accept the existing life; the environment that surrounds Martin Eden seems to be like a mirage to him.

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